

SCMS JOURNAL OF INDIAN MANAGEMENT

ISSN 0973 - 3167

Volume XVI Number 4
October - December 2019

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Scopus®

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Correlates of Financial Literacy: Strategic Precursor to Financial Inclusion

Dr. Mohit Kumar
Associate Professor and Associate Dean
IILM Academy of Higher Learning
Gomtinagar, Lucknow
Email: mohitahuja008@gmail.com

Rishish Mishra
Research Scholar
Department of Rural Management
Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University
Lucknow
Email: rishish.bbau@gmail.com

Prof. Kushendra Mishra
Professor
Department of Rural Management
Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University
Lucknow.
Email: kushendra78@gmail.com

A b s t r a c t

The paper discusses the contemporary relevance of financial literacy followed by present need. The primary objectives of the present paper are to establish the relationship between financial literacy and financial inclusion and to analyze the determinants of financial literacy and test the association of these determinants with the key demographic profile. The paper is based on primary data which has been sourced from face to face interviews using the structured schedule as a data collection instrument. The detailed research design and scope have been discussed in the paper.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Financial Literacy, Inclusive Finance, Money Management.

Personal finance or Wealth management is a buzz word in most developing nations these days. It has already achieved its fore in developed nations where it has completely transformed the lifestyle of the people. It is concerned with making the best of use of available pennies and to create a substantial base from a very meagre one. It basically plans an individual's income and other financial resources in such a way that the gap between expenses and income is nullified. It emphasizes on basic tenets of financial management which underlines better planning and control of available resources. The idea of personal finance has caught up with the academicians in a developing nation like India as well and it has found a lot of practical relevance considering the low levels of disposable income on one hand and high levels of financial mismanagement on the other hand. There has never been a culture of saving money in Indian people creating serious problems for those who have scant financial resources up their sleeve. This is one of the major hurdles for the policymakers who have failed to take this into the account and have come up with a series of myopic policy decisions. Finance has always been a major part of decision making in most families and it has a serious intervention while coping up with financial exigencies. The wise and efficient use of resources to maximize the benefit of each rupee would always play a greater role in managing efficiency of the overall financial system. Personal finance does have a strategic role to play in the context of the development of a nation which has a limited resource base.

The term financial literacy has motivation derived from the concept of personal finance. It simply states the person's ability to manage financial resources in an optimum manner. The economic development of the nation largely depends upon the way people get an access to the formal financial system and the way they get an access to various benefits derived from the host of economic policies. Therefore, a lot of talks has been with reference to inclusive growth & development and financial inclusion has been marked out as one of the handy tools available for achieving the same. A number of policies have been formulated and executed and each one has only spurred up the economic growth curve by a few notches only to become slow and sluggish in the far end. One of the reasons has been the fact that the appetite of the people have become saturated once they end up buying a financial product or a service and the other fact is that the level of content with a traditional financial product like a savings bank account among the people has been reasonable.

Hence, it becomes imperative that spreading concepts of financial knowledge and awareness needs to be expedited. Such an activity would only scale up the financial literacy levels of people which can ease up the intake of financial services.

The ability of people to manage resources and financial awareness along with higher levels of financial knowledge would only become better which can capitalize upon the host of policies aimed at financial inclusion and subsequent inclusive growth and development. The current study delves into the basics of personal finance and wealth management with an understanding of financial literacy and its relationship and interdependence with financial inclusion. It aims to provide for a research gap and the missing link between two important drivers of sound financial growth and sustainable financial system.

2.0 Review of Literature

2.1 History of Financial Literacy

The issue of financial knowledge, financial awareness and financial literacy has gathered momentum over the last decade. It has been a subject matter of interest for academicians, researchers, businessman, government and policy makers. A number of inputs have been made in the above area by researchers as a part of the survey undertaken for policy formulation.

Hogarth (2002) described financial literacy as the knack to discern between a plethora of financial choices available and selection of the one which can optimize the returns. It includes the ability to discern financial choices, discuss money and financial issues and plan for the future.

Beal and Delpachtra (2003) argued that a financially capable person should have a mindset to responsibly manage the financial affairs to an extent which is an effective one. This should be in addition to the fact that he should also have an ability to comprehend the usage of financial products and services and should have a working knowledge of financial system components. He should be adept at managing various money management issues. It talks about the mix of skills inculcating dimensions of knowledge and confidence as well.

Coussens (2004) emphasized in his work that concerns such as innovation in financial products, relative technological advancements, restructuring of the financial system,

changes in attitude towards risk and retirement should be taken into account as these underline the sea of change happening in the financial landscape of the globe.

Vitt et al. (2005) demarcated financial education as a process which helps the people to develop skills required to make informed decisions and take actions which can improve their financial position.

Hogarth J. M. (2006) established in his research that financial education consists of subparts and it is about being educated and being aware of the issues of managing money and every other financial concern. Further, he also stated that it is about understanding the basic concepts related to money management and other allied assets.

Atkinson et al., (2006) defined financial literacy as a combination of financial knowledge and financial behaviour related to money management. It can be summarized as a set of financial skills and individual behaviours.

Lusardi and Tufano (2008) also focused on the debt component of finances. They defined financial literacy as the ability to make decisions regarding the debt holdings one needs to undertake focusing on how one can implement basic knowledge about the time value of money and the concept of compounding measured in the case of everyday financial decisions.

In a nutshell, we can say that most definitions of financial literacy revolve around the concept of financial knowledge and understanding of basic financial products and services and the ability to plan and execute financial decisions.

2.2 Need for Financial Literacy

Hogarth (2002) found that financial literacy is vital as people are more educated and informed to make better decisions for families which in turn provides them with financial security and contributing to foster community development.

Hilgert, Hogarth, & Beverly (2003) agreed that financial knowledge primarily seems to be closely related to financial behaviour.

Lusardi and Mitchell (2007) coined the term financial literacy as a concept which is familiar with the most economic necessity for making savings and investment decisions. Financial literacy provides for practices and principles of financial markets, institutions, instruments and financial rules, regulations and procedures.

Lusardi and Tufano (2009) found that low levels of financial literacy results into a weak understanding of basic financial concepts and poor judgment in making other financial decisions related to spending and borrowing resulting from poor financial management. This has an adverse impact on financial decisions taken at household and individual levels.

In a similar study, Mandell (2009) stated that financial literacy seems to have a positive impact on financial behaviour and however the effect of financial education on financial behaviour is less certain.

Jariwala and Sharma (2011) confirmed that lower levels of financial literacy and financial education will result in unhealthy ways of financial decision making and financial planning.

Financial literacy is important both for the investor and the community as well. Education is all pervasive and leads to a change in behaviour on most counts while information has a lower scope and not necessarily may bring the desired outcome.

2.3 Literature on Financial Inclusion

Carbo et al. (2005) defined financial exclusion as the incompetence of some groups to access the financial system either due to voluntary or involuntary reasons such as access, prices, conditions or marketing.

Kamath, (2007) defines Financial inclusion as the process of ensuring access to timely and adequate credit and financial services by vulnerable groups at an affordable cost.

Rangarajan Committee (2008) provided an operational definition of Financial Inclusion. Financial Inclusion hence may be defined as the process of securing access to financial services and timely and adequate credit at an affordable price when needed by weaker sections of the society.

NABARD Report (2008) emphasizes on financial inclusion as access to basic formal financial services at an affordable cost in a sustainable manner for the vulnerable people

Raghu Ram Rajan Committee (2011) corroborated the concept of financial inclusion by defining financial inclusion as universal access to a wide range of financial services at a reasonable cost. Financial services not only include banking products but also other financial services.

2.4 Framework of Financial Literacy

World Bank (2009), Vitt et al (2005), Atkinson et al (2006) suggest that Financial literacy has been taken to mean so many things: knowledge and understanding of formal financial products and systems; familiarity with formal financial services; confidence to use new services, ask questions, and seek redress; skill to manage credit; and ability to plan ahead and budget

In 2006, Hungary undertook a survey of 'financial literacy' among residents aged 14 to 30 years old. The major topics covered were: general financial knowledge; money transactions; bank cards; lending; and retirement saving.

The Retirement Commission and ANZ Bank in New Zealand studied the levels of financial knowledge amongst adults in that same year (ANZ and Retirement Commission, 2006). They focused on five areas of financial knowledge: math, standard literacy and the understanding of financial records; financial understanding; financial competence; financial planning; and consumer rights.

CentiQ (2007) in his research revealed that the Netherlands also published a baseline study of 'financial insight' and financial behaviour amongst adults aged 18 and over. Financial insight was assumed to lead to financial behaviour and included motivations, knowledge, skills and perception.

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Statement of the Research Problem

The issues of financial rejuvenation and restructuring have been major concerns in India and financial inclusion has always been seen as an instrument to overcome the same. Financial inclusion movement in India has always tried the delivery of banking services at an affordable cost to the disadvantaged and low-income groups. Financial literacy is one of the pre-essentials that would ensure speedy acceleration of the financial inclusion initiatives.

It also emphasizes on the undercurrent that the financial resources with the people are managed only partially. No such work has been done before in the districts taken up for the study but it is pretty much evident that more and more work would be taken up in the area of financial literacy and extended financial literacy commonly known as financial literacy.

The study undertaken assesses the levels of financial literacy of people in regions of Lucknow, Kanpur Dehat and Gautam Budh Nagar.

So far not a lot of work has been done in the area of financial literacy in Uttar Pradesh so as to find answers to as to how the people save and why they save, areas where the people spend and why they spend, their attitude towards financial planning and control etc. This study starts with an exploratory analysis to uncover facets regarding financial behaviour and subsequent financial literacy.

3.2 Research Gap

3.2.1 The levels of financial literacy vary across the demographic and socio-economic profile underlining the need to establish a tangible relationship and association between the related variables.

3.2.2 There is a relationship between financial inclusion and financial behaviour. However, the nature, extent and direction of the relationship are unknown.

3.3 Objectives of the Study

3.3.1 To establish the relationship between financial literacy and financial inclusion in Uttar Pradesh, India.

3.3.2 To analyze the determinants of financial literacy and test the association of these determinants with the key demographic profile.

3.4 Research Hypotheses

The research is designed on the basis of the following hypotheses:

H₀: There is no relationship between financial literacy and financial inclusion of the people.

H₀: There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the gender of the people.

H₀: There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the age of the people.

H₀: There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the location of the people.

H₀: There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the education of the people.

H₀: There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the income levels of the people.

H_0 : There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the occupation of the people.

3.5 Research Design

The research design is a mix of conclusive and exploratory research design wherein an attempt has been made to initially derive a conceptual framework of financial literacy and then use the same framework to arrive at a measure of financial literacy.

3.5.1 Sampling Design

Sampling design is a concrete plan for drawing or selecting a sample from a given population.

3.5.1.1 Population

All adults above the age of 18 in Uttar Pradesh, India form the universe for the study under consideration. Various bank officials and people linked with financial inclusion were also interacted while forming the conceptual framework for the study.

3.5.1.2 Sampling Unit

A sampling unit is an object for which the data is gathered. For this study, all individuals in the districts of Lucknow, Kanpur Dehat and Gautam Budh Nagar are considered as the sampling unit.

3.5.1.3 Sample Size

The sample size is 600 adults above the age of 18 from the districts of Lucknow, Kanpur Dehat and Gautam Budh Nagar each contributing to 200 adults. The sampling frame included all the adults above the age of 18 in districts of Lucknow, Kanpur Dehat and Gautam Budh Nagar.

3.5.1.4 Sampling Technique

Sampling techniques are categorized into two groups as probability sampling techniques and non-probability sampling techniques. A multi-stage sampling technique is employed for the selection of the necessary sample of respondents. Initially, the three districts of Lucknow, Kanpur Dehat and Gautam Budh Nagar are selected on the basis of non-probability judgmental sampling. The

underlying judgment behind such a selection is that all the three districts scored high on levels of financial inclusion on CRISIL Inclusix 2013. The final selection of the sample was done using convenient sampling method while selecting the adults above the age of 18 years from the selected districts.

3.6 Primary Data

The primary data was collected from respondents from three districts by conducting face to face interviews using the structured schedule as a data collection instrument. The instrument was developed after comprehensive discussions with various participants such as bank officials and the targeted respondents as well as members of Self Help groups.

3.7 Research Instrument

The survey was developed to understand the impact of financial literacy on financial inclusion. The research instrument was tailored accordingly. Initially, preliminary research instrument was prepared based on in-depth literature review in the same and/or similar field.

3.8 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is delineated to analyze the Financial Literacy of the people of Uttar Pradesh, India. The districts so chosen from the state are Lucknow, Kanpur Dehat and Gautam Budh Nagar considering that they rank high on CRISIL Inclusix 2013.

4.0 Data Analysis

4.1 Reliability of Measurement

Reliability is an indicator of the level of uniformity between various measurements of a variable (Hair et al., 2009).

The evaluation of the uniformity of the entire measurement scale can be measured through the reliability estimates. The most important of all these is Cronbach's alpha. Hair et al. (2009) researched that the agreed upon lower limit for the estimate is 0.7 and it could be even 0.60 for some specific researches. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value for the scale is 0.751 indicating high level of internal consistency in the scale items. The value of Cronbach's Alpha is acceptable and desirable, as these values are more than 0.700, confirming that the scale is reliable enough to be used for further analysis. (Table 1)

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha for the Variables

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.751	44

4.2 Measurement of Financial Inclusion

The inclusion of financial services also needed to be measured to gauge the extent to which financial inclusion has been achieved in the three districts from the demand point of view. The index is a sum of having a savings product, insurance product, credit product or a miscellaneous financial service. Each of the subcomponents has an equal weighting. The basic premise for using the above subcomponents for arriving at a measure is the fact that these are basic financial inclusion service which an individual must be supplied with as per the economic policy of the government.

4.2.1 Dimensions of Financial Inclusion vs. Location

The data in Table 2 indicates the distribution of financial services across the locations. It is found that majority of the

respondents have a savings product from a formal banking system highest been in Kapur Dehat. Most of the respondents also have subscribed to one or the other insurance policy. The instance of having an access to an insurance product is again maximum in Kanpur Dehat followed by Gautam Budh Nagar and Lucknow. The percentage of the total respondents who have an access to a credit product is not a remarkable one and is less than the respondents who have an access to a saving product or an insurance product. The percentage of the respondents who have denied to use other financial services is also very high and is highest in Gautam Budh Nagar followed by Kanpur Dehat and Lucknow.

Table 2: Dimensions of Financial Inclusion vs. Location

Location		Kanpur Dehat		Lucknow		Gautam Budh Nagar	
		Count	% of Total	Count	% of Total	Count	% of Total
Saving Product	No	20	3.30%	32	5.30%	31	5.20%
	Yes	180	30.00%	168	28.00%	169	28.20%
Insurance Product	No	44	7.30%	65	10.80%	61	10.20%
	Yes	156	26.00%	135	22.50%	139	23.20%
Credit Product	No	113	18.80%	106	17.70%	131	21.80%
	Yes	87	14.50%	94	15.70%	69	11.50%
Misc. Service	No	118	19.70%	103	17.20%	122	20.30%
	Yes	82	13.70%	97	16.20%	78	13.00%

4.2.2 Financial Inclusion Index and Location

The Table 3 suggests that the level of financial inclusion from the demand perspective is maximum in Kanpur Dehat followed by Lucknow and Gautam Budh Nagar. Only 10 % of the respondents in Kanpur Dehat have a low level of financial inclusion while a significant 22% of the respondents in Gautam Budh Nagar have a high level of

financial exclusion. Nearly 88% of the respondents in Lucknow have an above average performance when measuring on the financial inclusion scale while 90% of the respondents from Kanpur Dehat perform exceedingly well on the same scale as compared to less than 80% of the respondents from Gautam Budh Nagar.

Table 3: Financial Inclusion Score vs. Location

Location		Financial Inclusion (%)					Total
		0	25	50	75	100	
Kanpur Dehat	Count	1	18	74	89	18	200
	% within location	0.50%	9.00%	37.00%	44.50%	9.00%	100.00%
	% of total	0.20%	3.00%	12.30%	14.80%	3.00%	33.30%
Lucknow	Count	3	22	76	76	23	200
	% within location	1.50%	11.00%	38.00%	38.00%	11.50%	100.00%
	% of total	0.50%	3.70%	12.70%	12.70%	3.80%	33.30%
Gautam Budh Nagar	Count	2	42	80	51	25	200
	% within location	1.00%	21.00%	40.00%	25.50%	12.50%	100.00%
	% of total	0.30%	7.00%	13.30%	8.50%	4.20%	33.30%
Total	Count	6	82	230	216	66	600
	% within location	1.00%	13.70%	38.30%	36.00%	11.00%	100.00%
	% of total	1.00%	13.70%	38.30%	36.00%	11.00%	100.00%

4.3 Scale of Financial Literacy

The measure of the construct of financial literacy is derived from a linear summation of its sub-constructs:

1. Capability of Overall Financial Knowledge
2. Capability of Money Management
3. Capability of Planning Ahead
4. Capability of Making Financial Choices
5. Capability of Seeking Help

The scale is ranged from 1 to 5 where 1 indicates a low level of financial literacy and 5 indicates a high level of financial literacy.

4.3.1 Scale of Financial literacy vs. Location

Table 4 highlights the location wise distribution of the respondents in terms of their overall financial literacy levels. Kanpur Dehat scores highest towards the positive end of financial literacy scale as compared to Lucknow and Gautam Budh Nagar. Further, 66.5% of the total respondents in Kanpur Dehat score well on financial literacy scale as compared to 59.0% of the total respondents in Lucknow and 58.0% of the total respondents in Gautam Budh Nagar. Almost two-fifth of the total respondents in Lucknow and Gautam Budh Nagar have scored low on financial literacy levels.

Table 4: Scale of Financial literacy vs. Location

Location		Scale Of Financial literacy					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Kanpur Dehat	Count	15	52	68	46	19	200
	% of Total	2.50%	8.70%	11.30%	7.70%	3.20%	33.30%
Lucknow	Count	20	62	68	45	5	200
	% of Total	3.30%	10.30%	11.30%	7.50%	0.80%	33.30%
Gautam Budh Nagar	Count	21	62	81	27	9	200
	% of Total	3.50%	10.30%	13.50%	4.50%	1.50%	33.3%
Total	Count	56	176	217	118	33	600
	% of Total	9.30%	29.30%	36.20%	19.70%	5.50%	100.0%

4.3.2 Scale of Financial literacy vs. Gender

Table 5 highlights the gender wise distribution of the respondents in terms of their overall financial literacy levels.

It is found that nearly 61 % of the total males score from moderate to high levels of overall financial literacy and 63 % of the total females score on the same range highlighting the importance of financial literacy in both the genders.

Table 5: Scale of Financial literacy vs. Gender

Gender		Scale Of Financial literacy					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Male	Count	36	113	136	77	19	381
	% of Total	6.00%	18.80%	22.70%	12.80%	3.20%	63.50%
Female	Count	20	63	81	41	14	219
	% of Total	3.30%	10.50%	13.50%	6.80%	2.30%	36.50%
Total	Count	56	176	217	118	33	600
	% of Total	9.30%	29.30%	36.20%	19.70%	5.50%	100.00%

4.4 Determinants of financial literacy & association of these determinants with the key demographic profile.

4.4.1 Hypothesis 1

Ho. There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the demographic profile of the people measured in terms of location.

This hypothesis is tested with the help of Table 6 by using Chi-square Test.

Since the significance value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a difference in the financial literacy of people.

Table 6: Chi-Square Test between Financial literacy and Location

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.069	8	.014
Likelihood Ratio	19.308	8	.013
N of Valid Cases	600		

4.4.2 Hypothesis 2

Ho. There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the demographic profile of the people measured in terms of gender.

Since the significance value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore financial literacy varies according to gender.

This hypothesis is tested with the help of Table 7 by using Chi-square Test.

Table 7: Chi-Square Test between Financial literacy and Gender

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi - Square	11.128	4	.025
Likelihood Ratio	11.324	4	.023
N of Valid Cases	600		

4.4.3 Hypothesis 3

Ho. There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the socio-economic profile of the people measured in terms of education.

Since the significance value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, financial literacy of the people is associated with education.

This hypothesis is tested with the help of Table 8 by using Chi-square Test.

Table 8: Chi-Square Test between Financial Literacy and Education

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.472	8	.036
Likelihood Ratio	16.670	8	.039
N of Valid Case s	600		

4.4.4 Hypothesis 4

Ho. There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the socio-economic profile of the people measured in terms of occupation.

his hypothesis is tested with the help of Table 9 by using Chi-square Test.

Since the significance value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, occupation is associated with the financial literacy of the people.

Table 9: Chi-Square Test between Financial literacy and Occupation

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.635	4	.013
Likelihood Ratio	12.845	4	.011
N of Valid Cases	600		

4.4.5 Hypothesis 5

Ho. There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the socio-economic profile of the people measured in terms of monthly income

This hypothesis is tested with the help of Table 10 by using Chi-square Test.

Since, the significance value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a difference in financial literacy people having different monthly incomes.

Table 10: Chi-Square Test between Financial literacy and Monthly Income

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.785	8	.011
Likelihood Ratio	19.915	8	.015
N of Valid Cases	600		

4.4.6 Hypothesis 6

Ho. There is no significant association between overall financial literacy and the socio-economic profile of the people measured in terms of age.

This hypothesis is tested with the help of Table 11 by using Chi-square Test.

Since, the significance value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the financial literacy of people is associated with their age.

Table 11: Chi-Square Test between Financial literacy and Age

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.125	12	.026
Likelihood Ratio	23.180	12	.025
N of Valid Cases	600		

4.5 Regression Analysis 1:

To check the impact of financial literacy level on financial inclusion level, the financial inclusion level is considered as an independent variable and financial literacy is considered

as the dependent variable. The results of correlation and regression are shown in the table numbered from Table 12 to Table 14 with interpretation.

The results of the regression analysis performed for these two variables are presented below.

Table 12: Model Summary ⁻¹

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.734 ^a	.671	.643	.31085

A. Predictors: (Constant), Scale Of Financial literacy

Table 13: ANOVA ^a -1

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	420.689	1	420.689	4353.665	.000 ^b
1 Residual	57.784	598	.097		
1 Total	478.473	599			

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Inclusion

B. Predictors: (Constant), Scale Of Financial literacy

Table 14: Coefficients^a -1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.951	.040		99.885	.000
1 Scale Of Financial literacy	1.002	.015	.938	65.982	.000

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Inclusion

The regression analysis was done to measure the variation in financial inclusion level based on variation in financial literacy level. From Table 14, the following regression equation is derived.

$$\text{Financial Inclusion Level} = 3.951 + 1.002 (\text{Financial literacy Level})$$

In the present regression analysis, the measure of the strength of the association is given by the coefficient of determination denoted by R². From table, it can be seen that the R² value is 0.671, which shows 67.1 % of the variance in financial inclusion levels can be predicted by his/her financial literacy level.

In other words, approximately 33 % (1.000-0.671=0.329) in a person's financial inclusion cannot be predicted by his/her financial literacy level. The regression equation appears to be very useful for making predictions since the value of R² is close to 1. The last column of the same table —standard error of estimation provides a measure of how accurately the regression equation predicts values of the dependent variable. The smaller the value of the standard error of estimation is, better one can predict that the independent variable (i.e. Financial literacy level) account for the variance in the dependent variable.

The t-test value for the significance of individual independent variable indicates the significance at 95%

confidence level. The Table 13 shows that financial literacy level is statistically significant with a value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The result of F test is also significant with a value of 0.000, which allows a researcher to determine whether or not the linear regression was statistically significant. This indicates that the model is statistically significant at a confidence level of 95%.

Regression Analysis 2:

Multiple regression is an extension of simple linear regression. It is used when we want to predict the value of a variable based on the value of two or more other variables. The variable we want to predict is called the dependent variable (or sometimes, the outcome, target or criterion variable). The variables we are using to predict the value of the dependent variable are called the independent variables (or sometimes, the predictor, explanatory or regressor variables).

This research uses multiple regression to understand whether financial inclusion can be predicted based on sub-constructs of financial literacy in the form of general financial knowledge, money management capability, ability to plan ahead, ability to choose financial products and ability to seek help.

Multiple regression also allows you to determine the overall fit (variance explained) of the model and the relative contribution of each of the predictors to the total variance explained.

Then, the hypothesized relationship between components of financial literacy and financial inclusion may be written as:

$$I = m + \beta_1 C_1 + \beta_2 C_2 + \beta_3 C_3 + \beta_4 C_4 + \beta_5 C_5 \text{ eq.(iii)}$$

Where,

The variable I is termed the dependent variable (I = Level of Financial Inclusion); C₁, C₂, C₃ and C₄, C₅ is termed as the independent variable or explanatory variable (C₁ is Level of Money Management Capability, C₂ is Level of Ability to Plan Ahead, C₃ is Level of Ability to Choose Financial Products, C₄ is Level of Ability to Seek Help, C₅ is General Financial Knowledge); m is the constant term and β₁, β₂, β₃, β₄ and β₅ are the coefficient of the variable C₁, C₂, C₃, C₄ and C₅. The regression is carried out and results are displayed as follows.

From the Table15, the following regression equation is derived.

$$\text{Financial Inclusion} = 0.653 + 0.388 C_1 \text{ (Money Management Capability)} + 0.093 C_2 \text{ (Ability to Plan Ahead)} + 0.109 C_3 \text{ (Ability to Choose Financial Products)} + 0.240 C_4 \text{ (Ability to Seek Help)} + 0.24 C_5 \text{ (General Financial Knowledge)}$$

In the present regression analysis, the measure of the strength of the association is given by the coefficient of determination denoted by R². From Table 15, it can be seen that the R² value is 0.838, which shows 83.8 % of the variance in financial inclusion levels can be predicted by his/her financial literacy determinants.

In other words, 16 % (1.000-0.838=0.162) in a person's financial inclusion cannot be predicted by his/her financial literacy determinants. The regression equation appears to be very useful for making predictions since the value of R² is close to 1. The last column of the same table —standard error of estimation provides a measure of how accurately the regression equation predicts values of the dependent variable. The smaller the value of the standard error of estimation is, better one can predict that the independent variable (i.e. Financial literacy determinants) account for the variance in the dependent variable.

Table 15: Model Summary-2

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.916 ^a	0.84	0.838	0.35921

a. Predictors: (Constant), Money Management Capability, Ability To Plan Ahead, Ability To Choose Financial Products, Ability To Seek Help, General Financial Knowledge

The t-test value for the significance of individual independent variable indicates the significance at 95% confidence level. The Table16 shows that financial literacy level is statistically significant with a value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The result of F test is also significant with a

value of 0.000, which allows a researcher to determine whether or not the linear regression was statistically significant. This indicates that the model is statistically significant at a confidence level of 95%.

Table 16: Coefficientsa-2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.653	0.228		2.864	0.004
Money Management Capability	0.388	0.036	0.453	10.891	0
General Financial Knowledge	0.024	0.014	0.044	1.791	0.047
Ability To Plan Ahead	0.24	0.046	0.233	5.191	0
Ability To Choose Financial Products	0.093	0.026	0.109	3.568	0
Ability To Seek Help	0.109	0.028	0.135	3.842	0

a. Dependent Variable: Financial In clusion

Conclusion

Based on data analysis some conclusions are presented as under:

- i. Most respondents have parked their savings in various investment alternatives, though the majority of the respondents possess lower levels of financial literacy. This shows that all respondents do not understand the basics of financial management.
- ii. This study depicts that financial literacy is a growing priority in all developed and developing countries. The review of past research studies coupled with the current study highlights a few critical areas for further research in the field.

- iii. The analysis of financial literacy questions indicates that the majority of respondents are less financially educated on core areas of financial literacy and lack an understanding of some of the major important concepts of financial management.
- iv. It is essential to take care of specific age groups and income groups who have scored least in the area of financial literacy and financial inclusion.
- v. It is also found that for respondents with higher monthly income and higher age group are better prepared while selecting financial products and while seeking financial help.

- vi. Further, it is also seen that financial literacy has a strong association with financial inclusion and higher levels of financial literacy can increase the uptake of financial products and financial services.
- vii. The construct of sound financial literacy implies a better financial skill, behavior and attitude towards money management, planning of expenses and income, selection of financial products and services and seeking financial help.
- viii. The respondents place themselves in a better place to meet and manage expenses creating long-term goals and selecting apt financial products and services.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis and findings of the current research study, it suggests that financial education provide, policy makers and regulatory authorities need to promote financial capacity building exercises.

For Policy makers and Regulatory Authorities

- a) Greater focus should be given on financial education of the people before the age of 40. They are prone to making more miscalculations as there is greater financial incapability among the people at that age.
- b) More emphasis should be placed on the creation of financial education measures designed to press upon the need for retirement planning and other personal finance measures.
- c) It is suggested that females should be targeted to provide financial education and it should be seen as a necessary vehicle for women empowerment and encourage them to participate in the decision making at the household level
- d) There is an urgency to initiate the financial education program at a younger age in the lives of people which will ensure proper financial management skills and will inculcate a savings habit and adequate money management.
- e) There is also a need to consider personal finance as a specific subject in the syllabus for the secondary school students and the students at the undergraduate level.
- f) The people with lower income and those who work on casual basis have relatively lower levels of financial literacy.

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